

ISic3428

Funerary inscription of Alphia

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

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Autopsy

2018.13.03

Last Change

2020-12-21 - Jonathan Prag minor edits

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

found during works near so-called 'tomb of Archimedes' in constructing road from viale Augusto to Corso Gelone

Coordinates

37.078125, 15.281091

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Area archeologica della Neapolis, Orecchio di Dionisio e Teatro Greco

Physical Description

The lower part of the stone is broken off, and the stone is worn or damaged on all sides. Gentili suggests that it is the cover for a 'tomba a cassa'

Dimensions

Height 20.8 cm

Width 86 cm

Depth 45 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

lunate sigma and epsilon, alpha with straight bar, phi is circular

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 64 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Ἀλφία εϋ[---]

2. εὐσεβῆ χαῖρ[ε][---]

Apparatus

Εὐ[τύχη(?)], Gentili

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644823

Bibliography

Gentili, G.V. 1961. Nuovi elementi di epigrafia siracusana. *Archivio Storico Siracusano*. 7: 5-25. At 21-22 no.3 tav.II.1 and dr

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Photo J. Prag